

Current status of low trophic aquaculture and harvesting in the Nordic countries

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Report Summary

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Ágríp á íslensku:	<p>Ein af framtíðarsýnum í norrænu samstarfi er að Norðurlöndin verði sjálfbærasta svæði heims árið 2030 og þarf að kannaða allar leiðir til að auka sjálfbærni innan bláa hagkerfisins. Að borða fæðutegundir af lægri stigum fæðukeðjunnar getur hjálpað til við að draga úr kolefnisfótspori matvælaframleiðslu og jafnvel hjálpað til við varðveislu vistkerfa. Þetta þýðir að samhliða því að fæða jarðarbúa, erum við einnig að leggja fram jákvætt framlag í baráttunni gegn loftslagsbreytingum og hamla tapi á líffræðilegum fjölbreytileika, sem á endanum stuðlar að bættri heilsu sjávar. Fæðutegundir af lægri stigum hafa lítil umhverfisáhrif og geta jafnvel veitt umhverfislegan ávinning, dæmi um slíkar tegundir eru ýmsar þangtegundir, skelfiskur eins og kælingar og ostrur, beitartegundir eins og ígulker og sæbjúgu, svo og sumar tegundir ferskvatnsfiska. Þessar tegundir hafa yfirleitt mun lægra kolefnisfótspor en önnur matvælaframleiðslukerfi og aðrar matvælategundir.</p> <p>Í þessari skýrslu er ætlunin að kortleggja hvað er verið að rækta og veiða af þessum tegundum á Norðurlöndunum.</p>		
Lykilorð á íslensku:	Fæðutegundir af lægri stigum fæðukeðjunnar, Norðurlöndin.		

<p><i>Summary in English:</i></p>	<p>The current vision for continued Nordic cooperation is that the “Nordic region will be the world's most sustainable and integrated region by 2030”, where every avenue of sustainability within the blue sector must be explored. One alternative is to expand the production of familiar and novel food, particularly the marine production of Low Trophic Species (LTS) such as macroalgae (seaweeds), filter-feeding shellfish (e.g. mussels and oysters), grazers such as sea urchins and sea cucumbers, as well as some species of freshwater finfish. Therefore, there have been several reports recently, like “Food from the Oceans” pointing out the importance of LTS, notably herbivore filter feeders as a part of the solution for direct human consumption or, together with cultivated macroalgae, and a more ecologically efficient source of feed for the farmed marine carnivores (e.g. finfish, shrimp, etc.). Accordingly, eating LTS can help reduce the carbon footprint of food production as LTS can provide food with a smaller carbon footprint than other land-based meat production systems, and can also preserve ecosystems. This means that whilst feeding the population, we are also making a positive contribution to the fight against climate change and biodiversity loss, ultimately contributing to improved ocean health.</p> <p>The aim of this report is to analyse the current status of low trophic aquaculture and fisheries/harvesting in the Nordic countries.</p>
<p><i>English keywords:</i></p>	<p>Low Trophic Species, Nordic countries.</p>

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Background and goals of the projects

The current vision for continued Nordic cooperation is that the “Nordic region will be the world's most sustainable and integrated region by 2030”, in which 12 objectives for a green, competitive and socially sustainable Nordic Region were identified for the period 2021-2024. Given the importance of the Nordic region's aquatic sector, every avenue of sustainability within the blue sector must be explored (Nordic Council of Ministers, 2020). In the Nordic countries, production from aquatic sources has played an important socio-economic role and will, with controlled utilisation, hopefully, continue to do so for the unforeseen future. Key pillars in production are sustainability, competitive edge, and constant innovation.

By 2050, it is estimated that the Earth will be home to 10 billion people. Feeding the world is already a challenge today, and this raises an important question: How can we sustainably supply food to the increasing population now and in the years to come? The consumption of marine foods, especially fish, has seen a significant increase in demand worldwide during recent decades. This increase can be attributed to the recognition of fish and seafood as principal proteins promoting human health, but also as a solution for feeding the ever-increasing world population, resulting in high demand for increased food production and an urgent need to explore alternative sustainable food sources (Brugere & De Young, 2020). However, the world is facing unprecedented challenges in terms of climate change and achieving food security. One alternative is to expand the production of familiar and novel food, particularly the marine production of Low Trophic Species (LTS) such as macroalgae (seaweeds), filter-feeding shellfish (e.g. mussels and oysters), grazers such as sea urchins and sea cucumbers, as well as some species of freshwater finfish.

Therefore, there have been several reports recently, like [Food from the Oceans](#) pointing out the importance of LTS, notably herbivore filter feeders as a part of the solution for direct human consumption or, together with cultivated macroalgae, and a more ecologically efficient source of feed for the farmed marine carnivores (e.g. finfish, shrimp, etc.). Furthermore, the report “[The Ocean as a Solution for Climate Change](#)” produced by the Expert Group of the High-Level Panel for a Sustainable Ocean Economy, provided the first-ever comprehensive, quantitative analysis of the role that ocean-based solutions can play in the fight against climate change. One of the priorities for fisheries, aquaculture and dietary shifts, was a need to create incentives for lower trophic level aquaculture. Moreover, the report suggests that aquaculture could lower carbon emissions by shifting to low-carbon feed options and this was also the conclusion of the AquaVitae project (Marinho, et al., 2022).

Accordingly, eating LTS can help reduce the carbon footprint of food production as LTS can provide food with a smaller carbon footprint than other land-based meat production systems, and can also preserve ecosystems (Krause, et al., 2022). This means that whilst feeding the population, we are also making a positive contribution to the fight against climate change and biodiversity loss, ultimately contributing to improved ocean health.

Furthermore, LTS are key species in facilitating Integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA), which is a sustainable approach to aquaculture in which species from different trophic levels are cultured together. Species at the lower trophic level (usually plants or invertebrates) benefit from residual resources (nutrients and organic matter) not utilised by, or excreted from, the higher trophic species (typically finfish) in the system. The LTS can then be harvested in addition to the fish, to give the farmer more revenue through product diversification, or even to be fed back to the fish. This creates a circular system that can be more cost-efficient and reduce the environmental impact compared to the culture

of each species alone (Valenti, et al., 2023). The concept can be applied to different species in the Nordic and adapted and designed according to their requirements. Combined with strong structures enabling innovation, including technological and species diversification, there is a huge potential in the Nordic Region, to take the lead in LTS aquaculture and IMTA development, hence exploiting the largely untapped potential of this sector.

The aim of this project is twofold, to analyse the **current status** of low trophic aquaculture and fisheries/harvesting in the Nordic countries, and to **make recommendations** on how more food and biomass from those LT species can be obtained in a way that does not deprive future generations of their benefits. This report will focus on the current status of commercial exploitation of LTS in the Nordic countries.

Introduction

Through the centuries, the Nordic countries have established a long tradition of utilising the sea and marine resources. However, environmental conditions vary between the countries. The Faroe Islands, Iceland, and Norway all have highly exposed coastlines facing the fully marine North Sea and the Atlantic Ocean. The coastlines of Denmark and Sweden, however, have longer coastlines facing various environmental conditions from fully marine in the North Sea to the brackish Baltic Sea, while Finland is only associated with the Baltic Sea. This affects the countries' fisheries and aquaculture sectors heavily. There is also limited access to low-populated coastlines with favourable currents and temperatures in the area, affecting large-scale open-water aquaculture possibilities (Paisley, et al., 2010; Björnsdóttir, et al., 2018).

Low trophic species (LTS) refer to organisms that occupy the lower levels of the food chain. LTS in marine ecosystems typically include primary producers, primary consumers, and detritivores as described below:

Primary Producers – Microalgae (phytoplankton), macroalgae, and plants that produce energy via photosynthesis.

- **Macroalgae** e.g., red, green and brown macroalgae, e.g. dulce (red), kelp species (brown) or *Ulva* (green).

Primary Consumers - Herbivores or organisms that feed on primary producers.

- **Zooplankton** e.g., copepods, krill
- **Bivalves or filter feeders** e.g., oysters, mussels and tunicates
- **Herbivores that feed on algae:** e.g. sea urchins & abalone

Secondary consumers or detritivores and decomposers - Animals that feed on primary consumers, including many carnivores and omnivores (secondary consumers), and animals that feed on organic matter in sediments (detritivores)

- **Detritivorous invertebrates** e.g., some worms and crustaceans
- **Decomposers/Detritivores** e.g. sea cucumbers

This is a simplified classification, and specific rankings can vary based on ecosystem type and local food webs. Trophic levels can also be impacted by aquaculture production strategies, see Strand, et al., 2022, p. 62.

In the next section we will cover most of the low trophic aquaculture production in the Nordic countries, although there may be some small-scale production that are not included at this time. It varies between countries which species are produced, but this report gives a rough overview of the most common species and production methods.

Primary Producers - Phytoplankton, macroalgae, and plants that produce energy via photosynthesis

Macroalgae, also known as seaweed, are one of the largest unexploited global resources for the sustainable production of food, feed additives, industrial commodities, and petrochemical substitutes. They have been used as food, feed, and fertilizer for centuries and are one of the raw materials found in large quantities in the Nordic region. In addition to being widely found in local areas in the Nordic region, conditions are generally good for growing macroalgae with further processing in mind.

Macroalgae can be roughly divided into three main categories by colour: green, red, and brown. These categories can be quite different in terms of the nutrient content of the biomass, the bioactivity and life cycles, all of which are important for production. Additionally, differences are also found within species depending on the season, geography, and growth conditions. This is due to macroalgae being extractive species, absorbing nutrients, and contaminants from their surroundings (Eklund and Kautsky, 2003). As a result, it is possible to produce various products from macroalgae (Araújo, et al., 2021; Camarena-Gómez et al., 2022). Macroalgae are foreseen as a viable alternative protein source (Gunstheimer and Jahreis, 1998).

Macroalgae (e.g., kelp, seaweed)

Current status in macroalgae production/processing in Norway

Norway has the highest number of macroalgae aquaculture companies in Europe and is the number one producer in terms of volume (Dos Santos Fernandes De Araujo, 2019). This results from the recent Norwegian strategy encouraging research institutions, industries, and public authorities to develop a bioeconomy based on the production and processing of cultivated macroalgae (Stévant et al., 2017). However, despite the push to develop this industry, only 25 out of a possible 522 licensed sites in Norway are actually producing macroalgae. The industry is still relatively small and consists of 25 companies, employing 80 people with an annual production in 2023 of 137 tonnes (Algae). Most of the cultivated macroalgae is sugar kelp (*Saccharina latissima*) and market opportunities have restricted the growth of the industry in recent years. There are now efforts to diversify the production with other high value species such as dulce (*Palmaria palmata*). A limited number of other species such as *Ulva* spp., *Porphyra* spp., and *Palmaria palmata* are also handpicked for high-end users such as restaurants in recent decades. The main volumes of macroalgae utilised in Norway are wild harvested kelp with the use of trawlers and mechanical cutting. This harvesting activity started already in the 1960s and targets two main species: *Laminaria hyperborea* and *Ascophyllum nodosum* (Vea & Ask, 2011; Mac Monagail et al., 2017). The main product from wild harvested macroalgae is alginate. Unfortunately, these species are difficult to cultivate with long life cycles.

Current status in seaweed production/processing in Denmark

In Denmark, there is both harvesting and aquaculture of macroalgae. Macroalgae production in Denmark is on the rise, with companies like Dansk Tang and Pure Algae playing central roles. Dansk Tang harvests around 10 tonnes of macroalgae annually, which is sold both fresh and dried. Pure Algae uses advanced technology to produce macroalgae in closed land-based systems, enabling rapid production with minimal environmental impact.

The production of macroalgae in Denmark is not limited to food. Macroalgae is also used in cosmetics, animal feed, and as bioactive material in various industrial processes. Research and development in macroalgae production are growing, focusing on harnessing macroalgae's potential as a sustainable resource. Both harvesting from wild stocks and farming in controlled environments are employed as

production methods in Denmark. Harvesting involves collecting macroalgae from natural habitats, while farming entails cultivating macroalgae in designated areas or closed systems.

HARVEST

Commercial harvesting of macroalgae in Denmark is still relatively small in scale and limited to a few coastal areas with sufficient biomass to support commercial needs. It is estimated that a handful of Danish companies harvest macroalgae from wild stocks for commercial use, most of which are sole proprietorships. Additionally, there are a few larger companies with fewer than ten employees. The harvested quantities per company vary from a few hundred kilos per year to a few hundred kilos per week, with the primary species being bladderwrack (*Fucus vesiculosus*) and serrated wrack (*Fucus serratus*). Harvesting is typically done with hand tools (scissors/knives) from the shore, or in some cases, in deeper waters using divers or snorkelling. Some companies also employ alternative harvesting strategies, such as using fishing nets to collect free-floating macroalgae or mechanized telescopic hedge trimmers.

FARMING

Macroalgae farming in Denmark has experienced steady growth, driven by the increasing demand for sustainable and healthy food sources. However, most activities are still centred around research and development projects aimed at utilising macroalgae for food, feed, and environmental benefits. These initiatives strive to create a circular flow of nutrients and support sustainable marine resource management and business development. Overall, Denmark is making significant progress in macroalgae farming, with a strong emphasis on sustainability, innovation, and commercial success.

Several companies have emerged in this sector. For instance, OceanWide Seaweed is at the forefront, developing innovative and sustainable farming techniques that enable large-scale and profitable cultivation of macroalgae, such as the red algae Dulse. Another example is MariPure, which focuses on developing feasible production strategies for methane-reducing macroalgae species. Their research and development efforts are aimed at creating scalable and cost-effective solutions that can be integrated into existing agricultural practices.

For many of these start-up companies, European funding has played a crucial role in attracting investors and scaling up operations for macroalgae cultivation, thereby demonstrating its commercial viability.

Overall, macroalgae production in Denmark is a dynamic and expanding sector with significant potential for sustainable development and innovation and the collaborative efforts of research institutions, innovative companies, and supportive funding mechanisms are positioning Denmark well in the European macroalgae industry.

Current status in macroalgae production/processing in Iceland

The macroalgae industry in Iceland has mainly been focusing on harvesting brown macroalgae species from wild sources but some startups have been evaluating the cultivation of red, green and brown macroalgae species, both onshore and offshore (Matvælaráðuneytið, 2023).

Companies, such as Hyndla, Lava Seaweed, Fine Food Íslandica and Nordic Kelp are focusing on the cultivation of macroalgae biomass. Hyndla, a startup company located in Reykjanesbær, primarily focuses on onshore cultivation using borehole seawater (Hyndla, n.d.). Their focus has been on two

red macroalgae species, *Schizymenia jonssonii* and *Dulce* as well as the brown macroalgae species *S. latissima*, and *Ulva spp.* (a green macroalgae species). Lava Seaweed, another startup, has collaborated with Ocean Rainforest and HS Orka in the Circle Feed project to cultivate the red macroalgae species *Dulce* using water from onshore fish farming, geothermal heat and green energy, aiming to produce macroalgae as feed for cattle to reduce greenhouse gas emission (Lava Seaweed, n.d.; Nordic Council of Ministers, 2020). Fine Food Íslandica, based in Króksfjarðarnes in the west of Iceland, is a small-scale offshore macroalgae cultivator, specializing in the cultivation of *S. latissima*, primarily for use as a food ingredient (Fine Foods Íslandica, n.d.). Lastly, Nordic Kelp is exploring the potential of cultivating brown macroalgae such as *Alaria esculenta* in Patreksfjörður with the hope to potentially integrate it with salmon farming in the future (200 mílur, 2022).

Besides the main macroalgae harvesting and cultivation companies in Iceland, some producers of cosmetic products, such as Tamar have been using Icelandic macroalgae in their skincare products with promising results (Tamar, 2024).

Current status in macroalgae production/processing in the Faroe Islands

The Faroe Islands have favourable conditions for farming macroalgae. There are currently 2.3Km² (230 ha) licensed to macroalgae aquaculture allowing the production of three brown species such as *S. latissima*, *Laminaria digitata* and *Alaria esculenta* and two red species *Dulce* and *Porphyra umbilicalis* (Wegeberg, et al., 2024). Macroalgae cultivation in the Faroe Islands began in 2005 with the Nordic Seaweed project, where initial trials on *A. esculenta*, demonstrated significant potential (Húsgarð Larsen et al., 2022). Two companies were established in the following years, Ocean Rainforest and TARI – Faroe Seaweed. These two companies have distinctive production methods and operate at different scales. On the one hand, Ocean Rainforest was established in 2007 and the first macroalgae cultivating rig was deployed in 2010. The company has established an innovative system for cultivating macroalgae under open ocean conditions (Bak et al., 2018). The company has a license to cultivate *S. latissima*, *L. digitata* and *A. esculenta*. Their operations are amongst the largest in Europe with over 220 ha in Funningsfjörður and Gøtuvík. Their processing plant in Kaldbak, was acquired in 2017 and is equipped for cleaning, packaging, freezing, drying, and ensiling (Ocean Rainforest, 2024). On the other hand, TARI – Faroe Seaweed was established in 2016. The company cultivates and harvests in the wild, with a focus on edible macroalgae species. TARI – Faroe Seaweed was granted licenses to cultivate *P. palmata*, *Porphyra umbilicalis*, *S. latissima* and *A. esculenta* in Kaldbaksfjörður. Additionally, TARI was permitted to establish a land-based facility in Fámjin for propagating materials and seeding ropes for further cultivation. TARI's more artisanal operations encompass hatching, aquaculture, harvesting, processing, packing, and sales, with a focus on sustainable biology and minimal environmental impact (TARI - Faroe Seaweed, 2025).

As in Europe, the macroalgae aquaculture in the Faroe Islands has the potential to expand and the area demand for macroalgae cultivation in the Faroe Islands thus will increase correspondingly (Wegeberg et al., 2024). This industry's expansion is driven by the EU's strategic goal to sustainably expand its aquaculture operations, placing algae farming as a central contributor to achieving the EU Blue bioeconomy and contributing towards the objectives of the European Green Deal. This industry however faces multiple challenges such as environmental, economic, political and market related, that need to be considered when analysing its expansion potential.

Current status in macroalgae production/processing in Sweden

Macroalgae farming in Sweden is an emerging industry with a strong focus on sustainability, innovation, and local resource utilization. With its long coastline and access to cold, clean waters, Sweden is well-positioned to cultivate a variety of macroalgae species. Cultivation of macroalgae in Sweden is strongly promoted on the political level as exemplified in the national aquaculture strategy and action plan. The current production started off as research projects that have expanded to commercial activities (Franzén, et al., 2024), and there remains a strong link between the research environment and commercial activities. There is now a handful of companies that together produced just over 80 tonnes of farmed macroalgae in 2022 (Toth and Liljenström 2023). The largest company is Nordic Seafarm. Smaller producers include Kobb, Blue fields, and Ten Island Seafarm. Several companies produce kelp as a side business within family-owned business. This production is complemented by wild harvest of macroalgae, also often run by small business and with a focus on nature and gastronomic tourism. Hence the volumes of wild harvested macroalgae are limited, and the activities are directed towards a premium market.

The most commonly farmed species is sugar kelp (*S. latissima*) and commercial production of the green algae sea lettuce, *Ulva fenestrata*, has commenced. The production typically uses longline systems, but the production of seedlings is done in flow through land-based systems. In the pipeline are other species in the *Ulva* Spp. (green algae), *Gracilaria* Spp. (red algae) and *Pyropia* Spp. (previously *Porphyra*) genus and the red algae Dulce (Toth & Liljenström, 2023), and there are ambitions to develop direct seeding techniques. There was commercial production of the red sea plume, *Asparagopsis taxiformis*, by one company as a supplement to diets for cows (Taylor, 2021) but the production is now paused.

There is significant effort being directed into improving harvesting processes and post-harvest processing of the produced macroalgae. Efforts include studies on fermentation, drying and product development. In the food sector, macroalgae is processed into nutrient-rich products such as snacks, seasonings, and supplements, appealing to a growing consumer demand for plant-based and sustainable foods. Beyond food, Swedish companies are exploring innovative uses for algae in bioplastics, biofuels, cosmetics, and pharmaceuticals. For example, algae-based packaging materials and skincare products are gaining traction as sustainable alternatives to traditional counterparts.

Microalgae

Sweden also has increasing production of microalgae, and there is clear interest in microalgae research and production. A few companies produce microalgae commercially, of which one (the Swedish Algae Factory) is cultivating marine diatoms. Production takes place in greenhouses in horizontal raceway systems and relies on artificial LED lighting. The algae produced in Sweden are used predominantly for cosmetics and nutraceuticals, but novel applications are emerging, such as increasing solar panel efficiency and antibody drug conjugates (Swedish Algae Factory, 2023).

Iceland has good condition for production of microalgae, and a few companies are production microalgae product commercially. VAXA is creating a new category of protein-rich and Omega-3 products for people and for fish feed on a large scale. Algalif is using *Haematococcus* for production of astaxanthin and baker's yeast for production of Beta-Glucans. There are several other companies in Iceland working with microalgae, but at smaller scale than Vaxa and Algalif, but are planning to scale up production.

Primary Consumers - Herbivores or organisms that feed on primary producers.

Primary consumers are typically herbivores, meaning they feed on primary producers (such as plants, algae, or photosynthetic organisms). In an ecological food chain, primary consumers are at the second trophic level, with primary producers like phytoplankton, algae, and plants that produce energy via photosynthesis at the first trophic level. Primary consumers play a crucial role in transferring energy from primary producers to higher trophic levels, such as secondary consumers. Although herbivores are the most common primary consumers, some omnivores (which eat both plants and animals) can also be considered primary consumers if their diet is mostly plant-based in a given ecosystem.

Zooplankton (e.g., copepods, krill)

Zooplankton are crucial vehicles for transporting carbon (energy) from primary producers (phytoplankton) to upper trophic levels. Lipid-rich zooplankton, in particular, have come under increased scrutiny as they potentially represent an underutilized resource of oils (Olsen, et al., 2011). The catching of *Calanus finmarchicus* is a controversial subject, due to *C. finmarchicus*'s important role in the food chain, both for ecologically and economically important species, it is feared that direct catches could have negative effects on their population size with possible environmental and economic impacts (Bachiller, et al., 2018; Melle, et al., 2014; Utne, et al., 2012). Furthermore, due to the mesh size of the floating trawls used to catch *C. finmarchicus*, there is a risk of other zooplankton, fish- juveniles, and eggs following as by-catch (Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries, 2018).

Commercial catching of *C. finmarchicus* exists in Norway, with a set quota of 254.000 tonnes per year (Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries, 2018). The copepods are harvested to produce oil and protein. The products from *C. finmarchicus* are mostly intended for human consumption as their health benefits have been heavily investigated (Eysteinnsson et al., 2018).

There are companies in Vestmannaeyjar, south of Iceland that are experimenting with catching *Calanus*. However, these trials have so far only been very small-scale. There is currently no utilisation of zooplankton species in Sweden, Denmark or the Faroe Islands.

Herbivores that feed on macroalgae: e.g sea urchins, abalone

Herbivores that feed on macroalgae are commonly found in marine ecosystems. These animals play a crucial role in controlling algal populations and maintaining the balance of the ecosystem.

Sea Urchins

These spiny benthic invertebrates are known for grazing on various types of algae, including kelp and other macroalgae. This grazing has become problematic in many countries such as Norway where an estimated 5,000 km² have been grazed down by very high densities of sea urchins. The most valuable part of the sea urchins is their gonads, also known as the 'roe'. Sea urchins that are found at very high densities often do not have any roe, but it is possible to increase the size and quality of the roe, via roe enhancement, before transporting them live to market. This could increase the utilisation of the resource, particularly if it is possible to expand the popularity and distribution of the product into European markets. There can be ecological benefits to harvesting sea urchins, where they are too numerous, and are considered pests. They overgraze kelp forests and cause barren areas. This causes low nutritional availability, resulting in smaller sea urchins, with small gonads. Small gonads mean low-value sea urchins. Harvesting the sea urchins in these areas could mean that the kelp forests would re-establish, benefiting the entire ecosystem (Stefánsson, et al., 2017).

The most common method of harvesting sea urchins is diving, which is considered limited in some countries as it is very expensive due to regulations, is time-consuming and the limited diving distances of the harvesting divers. It is also highly weather-dependent. Other methods such as trapping are being developed while in countries such as Iceland dredging is very successful. In Norway high-tech harvesting solutions are being developed that are not disruptive to the bottom ecology.

Sea Urchin harvesting in Iceland

The green sea urchin (*Strongylocentrotus droebachiensis*) is commonly found in Iceland; it can be found all around the island except possibly around the south coast. Currently, the fishing area for sea urchins in Iceland is in the inner part of Breiðafjörður. Sea urchin harvesting by dredging started in 1993 and catches were highest the year after, or about 1,500 tonnes. After that the catches decreased until 1997 when they stopped completely. The reasons were both markets related but also linked to overfishing. In 2004 the harvesting started again and between 2007 and 2014 the harvest was between 126-146 tonnes and has been relatively stable recently with 121 tonnes harvested both in 2022 and 2023. The bulk of the catches comes from Breiðafjörður, but much smaller quantities have been caught in other areas. The season is from early autumn until early spring, or when the sea urchin size and roe content are acceptable (Marine & Freshwater Research Institute, 2023 a).

In the last ten years or from 2013 to 2023, on average, 88% of the sea urchins harvested in Iceland have been exported to the French market, making it by far the most important market for Icelandic green sea urchins (Statistics Iceland, 2024).

Sea urchin in Norway

In Norway there has been intermittent harvesting of sea urchins by several smaller companies over the past decade. This has been small scale for boutique markets and resulted in an annual harvest of less than 30-50 tonnes each year. There is significant interest in the harvest of large quantities of sea urchin biomass as a food source and/or for other applications to remove the sea urchin density and encourage the regeneration of macroalgae forests. The latter have been devastated by the large populations of sea urchins along the coast of Norway. At this point harvesting is still an issue in Norway with bottom trawling being illegal and commercial dive fisheries being severely restricted by the regulations and associated costs of diving. Efforts by volunteer groups and industry groups to harvest larger quantities of sea urchins are continuing and will depend on the development of a cost effective and efficient harvesting technique.

There is no production of sea urchins in Sweden, Denmark and the Faroe Islands.

Abalone

Abalone is one of the most expensive and exclusive seafood there is and is considered a delicacy in France, parts of Latin America, New Zealand, and Southeast/East Asia. Abalone is mostly traded fresh but sometimes frozen, dried, or canned. It is mostly sold to high-end restaurants. The size of the foot muscle as well as its quality, are price determinants of abalone. Their shells are also sold for decorations, jewellery, and furniture as they have a mother-of-pearl sheen. In fact, abalone is mostly used for jewellery in Brazil, where the shells of the native species *Haliotis aurantium* are popular. Production in Europe is highly dependent on reaching buyers who are willing to pay premium prices for the product. Canned abalone is more often used in home cooking while dried abalone is used in traditional medicine in some parts of the world. There has been an increasing demand for flavoured,

value-added products beyond just canning in some markets. Production within the EU is small-scale and focused on organic production using macroalgae feed. The main markets for abalone are in China and other Southeast Asian countries. Smaller markets exist in North America and Europe. *Haliotis tuberculata* (European species) and *H. discus hannai* (Japanese species) are the only species currently being produced within the EU, with France being the largest producer of the species *H. tuberculata*. However, production is limited, with France producing only several tonnes per year (EUMOFA, 2019; Arias, et al., 2022; Arias Hansen, et al., 2021; Pleym, et al., 2023).

Abalone farming in Iceland

Aurora abalone, an abalone farming company was formed in 2007 under the name Sæbýli, but the company builds on previous experience that dates back all the way to 1988. It focuses on farming *Californian Red Abalone* and *H. discus hannai* (Ezo Abalone) from Japan. All the farming takes place indoors, where heated seawater is used, but the prime temperature for abalone farming is 18-20°C. The company is planning on building a vertical farming station in Reykjanes that will produce around 200 tons per year in the beginning, with the option of expanding it to 1,000 tonnes per year in relation to market conditions. Some test shipments of Icelandic abalone have been sent to Germany for market trials (Guðmundsson, 2023).

Recently, the company lost part of its stock during a volcanic eruption that resulted in a prolonged loss of electricity, that affected the youngest and smallest animals. But they managed to save part of the breeding stock and are working on that currently. They have moved their facilities partly from the area that is affected by frequent volcanic eruptions closer to the place they are planning to build the new facilities (Guðmundsson, 2024).

There is no production of abalone in Sweden, Norway, Denmark and the Faroe Islands.

Bivalves (e.g., oyster, mussels)

Oysters and mussels are bivalve molluscs of significant ecological and economic importance, widely cultivated for food and environmental benefits. Key oyster species in the region include the invasive Pacific oyster (*Magallana* (previously *Crassostrea*) *gigas*), and native European flat oyster (*Ostrea edulis*), while mussels are represented by a species complex including *Mytilus edulis* (North Sea) and *Mytilus trossulus* (Baltic Sea). These species inhabit diverse environments, including intertidal zones and subtidal areas where they attach to substrates such as stones, shells, or each other, sometimes forming reeflike structures when occurring in high densities. Both oysters and mussels are filter feeders that contribute to ecosystem health by improving water quality through the removal of suspended organic particles and microalgae from the water column. This filtration activity supports nutrient cycling and enhances biodiversity in the 3D structures formed by the bivalves. Consequently, oyster and mussel farming not only provides a protein-rich food source but also offers ecosystem services.

There is no commercial bivalve production in the Faroe Islands, however research trials of blue mussels' farms, endemic to the Faroese fjords, were set up together with salmonid farms in two IMTA approaches to model mitigation potential of some of the environmental impacts of the fish farm. Mitigation potential of the blue mussels under farming conditions in the Faroe Islands was not significant however still with uncertainties (á Norðri, et al., 2023). More work can still be done in this area.

Blue mussel production in Denmark

Denmark has a longstanding tradition of bivalve fishery, encompassing blue mussels (*M. edulis*), common cockles (*Cerastoderma edule*), and European flat oysters (*O. edulis*). In recent years, however, due to the decrease of both blue mussel and European flat oyster stocks, aquaculture has surpassed the value of fisheries landings. The Danish LTA predominantly relies on suspended rope cultivation and on-bottom cultivation techniques for blue mussels. Initiated in the early 2000s', suspended rope culture has seen an increase in blue mussel production from 235 tonnes to over 10,000 tonnes between 2005 and 2022 (Landbrugs- og Fiskeristyrelsen, n.d.).

The primary region for suspended mussel cultivation is the Limfjorden, located in northern Denmark. Limfjorden provides numerous sheltered and relatively shallow areas (<10 m) where mussel farms, each a maximum of 19 ha, are established. Suspended mussel cultivation is conducted via longlines or tube+net systems, based on the natural settlement of wild seeds. Long-line farms yield production volumes between 400 and 600 tonnes, while tube+net systems can yield between 800 and 1,200 tonnes, with a production cycle of 9-18 months that is organically certified.

On-bottom mussel cultivation, also situated in Limfjorden, sources seeds from wild seed beds or suspended spat collectors within the region. Wild seed bed plots range in size from two to 255 ha, whereas plots for aquaculture sourced seed have a maximum size of 15 ha. The average seed stocking density measures 2.8 kg/m², and mussels are harvested two-four years post relay. Due to the on-bottom cultures being harvested by fishing vessels under a license, there is currently an absence of official data concerning bottom mussel production volumes, as the harvest from these plots is aggregated with wild mussel fishery landings.

Oyster production in Denmark

Since the early 1850s', the Limfjorden has harboured a wild population of European flat oysters (*O. edulis*). In 2014, the parasite *Bonamia ostreae* was detected in the Limfjorden, and by 2015, the Limfjorden lost its status as free from *Bonamia* and *Marteilia*. The *Bonamia* has caused a significant decline in the wild flat oyster population, leading to reduced quotas until 2022, when the fishery was no longer sustained. Since 2015, small quantities of spat produced by a local hatchery have been intermittently provided to the aquaculture industry. In 2024, adhering to stringent biosecurity protocols, larger quantities of hatchery-produced spat were made available for cultivation by the oyster industry in Limfjorden.

Pacific oysters (*Magallana gigas*) are not cultivated due to their invasive species status, however, there are some special licences given for research project cultivation of triploid Pacific oysters.

Blue mussel production in Iceland

Mussels (*M. edulis*) are known to be good for cultivation and are considered nutritious and environmentally friendly, while still being affordable. Mussel aquaculture has proven difficult to maintain in Iceland, ever since it started in 1988, due to predators, limited and unreliable availability of larvae, lack of environmental research, complex permitting systems, high cost of toxicology monitoring and more (MAST, 2023; Kristinsson, 2024). Mussels have mostly been cultured with a longline method (Kristinsson, 2024). Unlike many European countries, the Icelandic government does not financially support farmers monitoring toxins. They have to do it at their own cost. Additionally, new laws introduced in 2011 made monitoring and permit requirements stricter. On top of all this, no

equipment that measures these toxins currently exists in Iceland, so samples need to be regularly sent to Ireland, increasing monitoring costs considerably (Sveinsdóttir & Bjarnason, 2024).

Although Icelandic mussels are considered a sustainable high-quality product, the future of mussel aquaculture in Iceland is very unclear. Currently, there are 8 active permits for mussel aquaculture held by six different companies although none seem to be harvesting (MAST, n.d.). However, many remain hopeful that mussel aquaculture could become a significant industry for Iceland, especially in smaller, more rural towns and recently 16 municipalities around Iceland signed a petition to the government, encouraging them to investigate the potential of mussel production (Sveinsdóttir & Bjarnason, 2024; Reynisson, 2024). However, significant barriers would need to be overcome for production to become large-scale, creating opportunities for more research and innovation (Kristinsson, 2024).

Scallop production in Iceland

Between 1988 and 1991, Icelanders experimented with farming scallops in Breiðafjörður. The goal was to let larvae grow up to slaughter size, as only shells of a certain size were fished. The larvae were collected and raised in cages until reaching the correct size, which was considered to be two years earlier than they would in nature. However, since scallops grow slowly around the Icelandic coast, they may not be a profitable aquaculture species (Jónasson, 2007). Additionally, a collapse in the wild population and predatory starfish make finding larvae difficult (Ólafsdóttir, 2017). Currently, there are two active permits for scallop production in Iceland, held by two different companies (MAST, n.d.). However, it is unclear if they are producing anything. As for catching wild scallops, they were first caught in 1969, when 400 tonnes were caught in Ísafjarðardjúp. From 1970 to 2003, over 250,000 tonnes of scallops were caught, mostly in Breiðafjörður. However, in 2003 a fishing ban was put in place due to a decline in the natural population. The ban was lifted in 2014, but catches have been minimal since then with only 63 tonnes landed in 2022 (Marine & Freshwater Institute, 2023 b).

Oyster production in Iceland

Oyster production started in Húsavík, north Iceland, in 2013. Live Pacific oyster (*M. gigas*) spat was regularly imported from Spain over a few years. The Environment Agency of Iceland banned imports in 2019 due to concerns that they may become invasive. The imported spat was put in closed cages to mature and reach harvest size and then sold at restaurants within the country. This was the northernmost oyster aquaculture known at the time. The last known harvest of oysters in Iceland was in 2021. The reasons for its decline were both stricter importing requirements and an outbreak of Norovirus in 2018, which dramatically decreased the demand for oysters at the only restaurant that served them (MAST, 2023; Viðskiptablaðið, 2019).

Blue mussel production in Sweden

Blue mussel farming is the most widely produced marine organism in Sweden. The majority of the production is located in sheltered and shallow inshore waters in one specific area of the coast (around the Orust island). The most common method of mussel farming in Sweden is longline systems, but there are also small-scale community activities based on droppers hung from triangular raft structures. Seed are sourced naturally by deployment of seed collectors (fuzzy ropes or flat lines). There are indications from the industry that seed settlement has been reduced over time and is becoming more erratic, although 2024 was an unusually successful year for mussel recruitment. The

culture cycle of mussels in Sweden is two-three years, with little management of the production during this time. Harvest of mussel seed from Smartfarm systems (nets) for size sorting and socking has been evaluated but the technique is not implemented at scale. An exception to the lack of production management is efforts to control mussel predation by eider ducks. A number of techniques have been applied to manage mussel predation, e.g. scaring birds away with small boats and netting (Lindegarth, et al., 2019, pp. 45). The former method is now banned. The use of netting is challenging due to heavy loads of fouling, yet today constitutes one of the most applied methods. Autonomous drones (surface based) are being discussed as an alternative but have not yet been evaluated.

The production of mussels in Sweden has varied over time and peaked at almost 3500 tonnes in 2021 but has since shown a significant decrease to the current 1,700 tonnes (2023, Swedish Food Agency (SFA, personal communication M. Persson). In 2022, there were 23 active mussel farms operated by a lower number of enterprises, although the number of registered facilities was higher (54; Jordbruksverket, n.d.), and 67 men and 34 women were employed in the sector (Leonardsson, 2023). Site selection for new farms is primarily done through industry know-how of suitable production areas with good growth conditions, with a preference for sheltered areas and recently favouring areas outside of MPAs due to the requirements of a Nature 2000 impact assessment for establishment in such areas.

There has been no harvest of wild mussels in Sweden since the year 2000.

Oyster production in Sweden

Flat oysters (*Ostrea edulis*) have been harvested from wild populations for centuries in Sweden, but oyster aquaculture is a relatively new activity (Lindegarth, 2012). Wild harvest is done through handpicking during diving as dredging in shallow areas is banned. During the early 2000s', oyster seed were sourced using sea-based collectors, but since the establishment of the invasive pacific oyster (*Magallana gigas*) in 2006, the possibility of collecting native oyster seed using this technique is drastically reduced in most areas as pacific oyster seed, which often dominate in number, settle on the collectors (Strand et al. 2019). The culture of invasive pacific oyster is not allowed due to the recent establishment in the country (2006, (Wrange, et al., 2010). A flat oyster hatchery exists at Koster and has, for the past 15-years, explored the possibilities of producing seed of the native oyster (Strand, et al., 2019) recently with good success (millions of settled seeds produced). A range of techniques is used for oyster production, including longlines with suspended oyster baskets (Dark sea or Aquapurse type), surface based floating bags, and oyster baskets suspended from an above water mounted structure. Oysters in the latter two techniques are lowered to the bottom during winter. The culture cycle of flat oysters in Sweden is three-four years. The production is challenged with fouling and requires regular maintenance, at which time the oysters are also size sorted and oyster density in baskets is adjusted.

Since 2020, aquaculture production has increased and reached five tonnes in 2022 (SFA, personal communication M. Persson). The production has been hampered by a lack of seed but the recent success in the oyster hatchery opens possibilities for expansion. In 2022, there were three active oyster farms (Leonardsson, 2023), yet six registered commercial facilities (not all may be active; Jordbruksverket, n.d.). Additionally, several entrepreneurs also keep wild harvested oysters in live storage for tourism and gastronomic purposes. The production is primarily located in the Northern

part of the Swedish west coast. Site selection is primarily based on easy logistic access for the farmer, with a preference for sheltered areas. As for blue mussel production, MPAs and Natura 2000 areas are avoided due to administrative reasons. Swedish flat oysters are free from notifiable diseases, and seed and larvae have been provided to oyster restoration programs in Europe (Personal communication, Ostrea Production AB). Efforts are ongoing to classify Swedish waters according to EU legislation on notifiable diseases on shellfish.

In addition to wild harvest and aquaculture production, there is increasing harvest of wild Pacific oysters in Sweden. During 2018 and 2022, between 10-15 tonnes of oysters were harvested yearly. Harvest is done by hand; however, different techniques have been evaluated related to management harvest (e.g. dredging and excavator, Heß, 2024). The concept of management harvest of pacific oysters is increasingly explored in Sweden (e.g. the DynamO project; IVL, 2024) with the aim to harness the socio-economic benefits provided by the species at the same time as negative impacts are mitigated.

Other filter feeders

Another filter feeder being produced in Sweden is the sea vase (*Ciona intestinalis*, (Loo & Petersen, 2013). The species is produced using longline systems (Leonardsson, 2023). Research culture activities targeting biogas and fish feed have been ongoing since 2015 and up to 300 tonnes per year have been produced (Sinha, et al., 2022), but recently (2019) the species has also been harvested for food with a peak production of 65 tonnes in 2022 (SFA, personal communication M. Persson). The main company farming sea vase is Pronofa, which operates in both Sweden and Norway.

Secondary consumers or detritivores and decomposers; animals that feed on primary consumers, including many carnivores and omnivores.

Decomposers/Detritivores (e.g. Sea cucumbers)

Sea cucumber fisheries in Iceland

TAC was first recommended for sea cucumber by the Marine Research Institute (MRI) in 2009 for two areas in Faxaflói in south Iceland and Aðalvík in the western part. The initial advice was 350 tonnes in the west fjords and 950 tonnes in the south, which was based on 10% of the estimated abundance in each area (Marine & Freshwater Research Institute, 2019).

Since 2008 until 2023, the yearly catches have fluctuated greatly, from 848 tons in 2014 to 5,985 tonnes in 2018. Currently, their total allowable catch (TAC) is issued for eight different fishing areas. Recently, the catches were 2,822 tonnes for 2022 and 2,401 tonnes for 2023. The volumes were lower in 2021 due to the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on markets (Marine & Freshwater Research Institute, Iceland. 2024).

The bulk of the catches are frozen and exported to China where the raw material is boiled and repacked in consumer packaging. A small part of the catches is processed further in Iceland, that is boiled, dried and packed. The consumption in China has been changing, where the consumers are less interested in products that need to be rehydrated, and they are more interested in ready-to-eat products (Ólafsson, 2024).

Sea cucumber fisheries in Norway

In Norwegian waters, the deep-water species of red sea cucumber (*Parastichopus tremulus*) and the brown sea cucumber (*Cucumaria frondosa*) both have potential as seafood. Because they are only found in relatively deep water there is no established fishery, catch history is difficult to quantify and there has been very limited research scale aquaculture attempts in the past decade.

Sea cucumber aquaculture in Sweden

There are ongoing activities to develop a hatchery protocol for the sea cucumber *Parastichopus tremulus* (Schagerström, et al., 2022) but no commercial production has yet been established. The research activities have, however, shown a drastic decline in sea cucumbers which are now exceedingly rare in nature. Aquaculture production of sea cucumbers is therefore equally directed towards restoration activities as to grow out. A similar development, i.e., a focus on restorative activities, has also been developed for lobsters, flat oysters, and blue mussels, which is in alignment with Sweden's strong environmental sustainability focus. Consequently, a new direction within the Swedish aquaculture sector, restoration aquaculture products, is hence under development and is increasing.

Conclusion

As stated in the Food from the Oceans report (European Union, 2017); “According to the best available scientific knowledge, by far the biggest potential for increasing seafood production in the foreseeable future is through the farming of marine species (i.e. mariculture), especially those at lower levels in the ocean food chain. Eating LTS can help reduce the carbon footprint of food production as LTS can provide food with a smaller carbon footprint than other land-based meat production systems and can also preserve ecosystems. One of the main arguments for increasing low-trophic fisheries and aquaculture is decreasing the reliance on produced feed.

As we have summarized in this report, the Nordic countries covered in this report are utilizing the low trophic species to some degree. However, in many places there is potential to do much more regarding LTS, both regarding harvesting/fishing and aquaculture.

There are some barriers that the sector must overcome to increase availability. There are legal and regulatory barriers, often in connection with marine and maritime planning that can hinder harvesting/fishing and aquaculture development of LTS. Also, there seems to be a lack of knowledge among consumers on species from low-trophic aquaculture. This includes familiarity with them as food, cooking methods, origins and of their environmental and health benefits. This is believed to hinder the expansion, especially in local markets.

It is a worry, not only for the LT sector but also Nordic fishing and aquaculture sectors that seafood consumption is more common among older age groups, those with high incomes and those who are well-educated. The barriers to seafood consumption for young people seem to relate to a lack of time and cooking skills, but generally, there seems to be a lack of knowledge among consumers on low trophic species. This includes familiarity with them as food, cooking methods, origins and of their environmental and health benefits. This could hinder the uptake in some markets; however LT have huge potential for further processing and utilization, that could make these products more common on the consumer plate, in any form and shape. The Nordic counties must reap the full potential of these species with strategy on how to increase production and availability.

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